

Link Between Classical Statistical Mechanics and Quantum Mechanics for the Ground State of the Oscillator?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Mar. 14, 2019

In this note, we investigate two velocities present in a quantum bound state. The first is the root mean square velocity, which appears in the time independent Schrodinger equation as $(-1/2m(1/W) d/dx d/dx W) = .5m v(x)*v(x)$ where W is the wavefunction and $v(x)$ is equal to the classical velocity. The second is $(1/W) d/dx W(x)$ which is an average momentum flux related to the spatial derivative of the density. From Newton's conservation of energy, one has $Mvdv = -d/dx V(x)$. This formula can always be applied to the root mean square velocity in quantum mechanics, but usually not to the flux velocity. In the case of the oscillator, however, the equation holds for both velocities (up to a factor of 2 related to $d(x)=WW$). This is important as the flux velocity is related to $d/dx d(x)$, the change in density. In classical statistical mechanics, the spatial density $d(x)=C \exp(-V(x)/T)$ also leads to a relationship for $d/dx d(x)$, thus one can use this as a point for comparing quantum mechanics and statistical mechanics at least for the oscillator case. It can be noted that $\exp(-.5mv^2/T)$, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution implies a spatial density of $C \exp(-V(x)/T)$. The velocity and spatial distributions are not independent. Similarly, in quantum mechanics, spatial density is $W(x)W(x)$, but $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ of } \sin(px)$ so given a wavefunction, its Fourier transform is $f(p)$, the momentum distribution. The two are not independent. Finally, we try to show that for the case of the oscillator, one can obtain an expression for thermodynamic free energy in quantum mechanics, and show that $\exp(-ap^2)$ is an extremum for free energy.

Relationship Between the Spatial and Velocity Distribution in Classical Statistical Mechanics

In (1), a differential equation for $f(v)$, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, is obtained using the idea that two particles collide elastically. We list the argument here:

" $f(p_1)f(p_2) - f(p_3)f(p_4)$ where $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4$ and $K(p_1) + K(p_2) = K(p_3) + K(p_4)$

Here p_1 to p_4 are momentum vectors and K is the kinetic energy. For the relativistic case, K can be replaced with E , the energy. This criterion is based on scattering from p_1 and p_2 into p_3 and p_4 and guarantees equilibrium. One can immediately see that if $f(p)=\exp(-\text{quantity})$ where the "quantity" is conserved, one has a solution. Let us, however, consider the scattering of a momentum p into $p+dp$. Consider: $f(p)f(p_1)-f(p+dp)f(p_1')$ where we assume that p increases slightly. Then: $df/dp / f(p) = p/p_1 df/dp(p_1) / f(p_1)$ $p_1'*p_1'=p_1*p_1-2pdp$ and $f(p)=B\exp(-Ap^2)$ where A and B are constants."

Thus, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be obtained, it seems, from analysis of elastic two particle scattering at a point x . If a potential exists in the system, $V(x)$, then at x , one has

$\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ as the probability, but at x_1 (before x in time), $p^2/2m + V(x) = p_1^2/2m + V(x_1)$. This seems to imply that one must have a spatial density proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. In general, the probability would be $\exp(-p^2/2mT + V(x))$ so that it does not change for the same particle even though relative potential and kinetic energy values do.

The point to note is that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, obtained without reference to entropy, does not only give a relationship for the probability of v , but also for x . The two densities are not independent. One implies the other. This is interesting because quantum mechanics is similar. The spatial density is $W(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \sin(px)$, so given $W(x)$ one immediately has f_p , the momentum distribution. The two are directly linked by a Fourier transform.

Flux in Quantum Mechanics

The Schrodinger time-independent equation can be written as:

$$\left[(-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x)\right]/W + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

Where $\left[(-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x)\right]/W = .5mv(x)v(x)$

Here $v(x)$ is the classical velocity given by:

$$.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((2))$$

Thus, at each point, the quantum bound state satisfies conservation of energy with a root mean square velocity equal to $v(x)$, the classical velocity. If one takes the spatial derivative of ((1)), one obtains:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left\{ \left[(-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x)\right]/W \right\} = -\frac{d}{dx} V(x) = \text{Force}(x)$$

In other words, the force is related to the change in classical kinetic energy in quantum mechanics i.e.:

$$v \frac{dv}{dx} = - \frac{d}{dx} V(x) \quad ((3)) \quad (\text{Here } m=1)$$

There is also another velocity in quantum mechanics, namely:

$$(1/W) \frac{d}{dx} W(x) = \left[\sum_p p f_p \cos(px) \right]/W(x) \quad ((4))$$

This velocity represents a kind of average momentum p , while the kinetic energy average is:

$$\left[(-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x)\right]/W = \left[\sum_p p^2/2m f_p \sin^2(px) \right]/W(x) = .5mv(x)v(x)$$

The flux velocity in ((4)) is critical for describing the change in density:

$$d/dx d(x) = 2 W(x) d/dx W(x) \quad ((5))$$

In classical statistical mechanics, it is the spatial density which gives one information about the potential. In general, however, ((4)) does not satisfy ((3)) in quantum mechanics (while the root mean square velocity always does).

Let us consider a case in quantum mechanics where ((3)) is satisfied by the flux velocity. Then:

$$W d/dx(W) d/dx [(1/W) d/dx W] = -d/dx V(x) \quad (\text{only for an oscillator})$$

$$W d/dx(W) \{ -1/W^2 (d/dx W)^2 + 1/W d/dx d/dx W \} = -.5 d/dx V(x) \quad (\text{only for an oscillator}) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) allows one to see the relationship between the two velocities $v(x)$ v_{flux} as it can be written as:

$$v_{flux} \{ -v_{flux} * v_{flux} - .5 m v(x) * v(x) \} = -.5 d/dx V(x)$$

If $V=4ax^2$ and $W= \exp(-ax^2)$, ((6)) will be satisfied with $\exp(-ax^2)$ being a solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation, i.e. the ground state of the oscillator.

It should be noted that the term in $\{ \}$ in ((6)) is a constant for $\exp(-ax^2)$ and can be written as:

$-v_{flux} * v_{flux} - .5v(x) * v(x)$ Here m mass is set to 1. In (2), it was suggested that one could define a temperature in quantum mechanics using $v(x)v(x) - v_{flux} * v_{flux}$. It was erroneously stated that for the oscillator this temperature would be a constant. The $4ax^2$ terms do not cancel for this definition of temperature, but rather cancel for the term in $\{ \}$ in ((6)).

Now, for classical statistical mechanics:

$$d/dx d(x) = d(x) (-1/T d/dx V(x))$$

For the quantum mechanical oscillator:

$$2W d/dx W = d/dx d(x) = 2 d(x) (1/W) dW/dx = .5 d(x) (-d/dx V(x))$$

Thus, for the case of an oscillator, the form of $W(x)$ and hence $d(x)=W(x)W(x)$ is the same as that for classical statistical mechanics.

One may next ask about the distribution of p , namely f_p . In quantum mechanics, f_p is obtained from a Fourier transform of $W(x)$ and so one has $\exp(-bp^2)$ where b is a constant related to a . Thus, one has not only a Gaussian spatial dependence, but a Gaussian momentum distribution.

Free Energy in the Quantum Case

Using a Fourier transformation to relate f_p and $W(x)$ in quantum mechanics may not be as clear as one would like. It seems that one may consider another relationship using the idea of free energy which seems to hold for the case of the oscillator. If one takes the time independent Schrodinger equation and writes $V(x)W(x)$ as the product of two Fourier series, one obtains for each $\sin(px)$:

$$p^2/2m f_p \exp(ipx) + [\text{Sum } j+k=p V_j f_k] \exp(ipx) = E f_p \exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

One can cancel $\exp(ipx)$ and write this as:

$$[\text{Sum } j+k=p V_j f_k] = [E - p^2/2m] f_p \quad ((9))$$

For the case of an oscillator, we know that $f_p = \exp(-b/2mp^2)$, thus $p^2/2m f_p$ is of the form:

$(1/b) f_p \ln(f_p)$ which is like TS where T is temperature and S entropy. Thus ((9)) is equivalent to:

$$\text{Sum on } p [\text{Sum } j+k=p V_j f_k] = E - TS = \text{Free energy} \quad ((10))$$

If $\exp(-bp^2/2m)$ is a solution of ((10)) it should be an extremum of the equation. In other words, f_p should extremize the free energy for each p . Consider $f_{p+dg} = f_p + dg$ where dg is small. Then:

$$F(f_p + dg) = E(f_p + dg) - T \ln(f_p + dg) (f_p + dg)$$

To first order this is:

$$dF = Edg - Tdg \ln(f_p) - T f_p / f_p dg = (E - T) dg - T dg \ln(f_p)$$

A solution is to have $dg = C f_p$, thus dg has the same functional form as f_p and so it seems that f_p is an extremum of the free energy.

This seems to link f_p to classical statistical mechanics more clearly.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to argue that in quantum mechanics, there is a flux $(1/W)d/dx W$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. This flux is related to the change in density $d/dx W = 2 W dW/dx$. In classical statistical mechanics, the change in spatial density $d/dx d(x) = d(x) (-1/T)$

$d/dx V(x)$. In general, $1/W dW/dx$ is not simply related to $-dV/dx$ in quantum mechanics. Quantum mechanics has two velocities, $1/W dW/dx$ being a flux velocity and $(-1/2m) (1/W)d/dx d/dx W = .5mv(x)v(x)$, with $v(x)$ being the classical velocity. In general, it is this classical velocity, and not the flux velocity, which satisfies a conservation of energy equation. For the case of the oscillator, however, $1/W dW/dx$ also satisfies $2vd/dx v = \text{Force}(x)$. (Here an extra 2 is needed which is related to $d(x)=WW$). Thus, for the oscillator, the two velocities are consistent and quantum mechanics matches classical statistical mechanics in form. One can even show, it seems, that f_p for the quantum oscillator, is an extremum of free energy.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. On the Derivation of the Boltzmann Distribution (preprint, zenodo, 2018)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Temperature and Heat Flux in Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2019)